

Influence of fertilization on stem borer incidence on four rice cultivars

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The effect of two levels of NPK fertilization (80-40-40 and 100-50-50 kg/ha) on the incidence of the yellow rice borer *Tryporyza incertulas* was studied

on four rice cultivars—Ponni (Mahsuri), IR20, CO 38, and Bhavani (C4-63, from the cross Peta/BPI 76)—in a 1975 experiment.

Stem borer incidence was significantly lower in plots that received lower nutrient levels. Infestation was maximum in Bhavani and minimum in Ponni (see table). ❧

Effect of level of fertilization on stem borer incidence on different rice cultivars. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai, India.

Variety	Stem borer incidence ^a (%) at		Mean
	80-40-40 ^b	100-50-50 ^b	
Bhavani	9.2 (17.6)	10.2 (18.5)	9.7 (18.1)
CO 38	6.2 (14.4)	6.1 (14.3)	6.2 (14.3)
IR20	4.7 (12.1)	5.7 (13.7)	5.2 (12.9)
Ponni	2.1 (8.3)	2.7 (8.9)	2.4 (8.6)
Mean	5.5 (13.1)	6.2 (13.9)	

^aMean of 4 replications. Figures in parentheses are transferred values. Between varieties, significant at 1% C.D. (P=0.05) = 2.4. Between fertilization, significant at 5% C.D. (P=0.05) = 0.4.

^bKg/ha of NPK.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION Drought resistance

Some upland rice selections of international origin (IRTP) promoted for minikit tests in Karnataka, India

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Rice in Karnataka is grown over an area of 1.2 million ha. About 0.7 million ha is rainfed. In hilly and coastal sections, rainfed rice is transplanted; in the transition belts, it is drill-sown. Drill-sown rice occupies 0.2 million ha in Dharwar and Belgaum districts and in parts of Shimoga and northern Kanara. Farmers drill rice early in May and June under relatively dry conditions. The upland crop remains unflooded throughout most of the crop season. Seasonal rainfall ranges from 600 to 800 mm and the rice crop (upland and wetland) is often subject to drought.

A range of locally adapted rice

varieties is grown. Some are dryland types such as D6-2-2 and Waner 1. Others are grown as semidryland rice (A67 and M161) or wetland rice (Y4 and HY26-lo), or both. These ecotypes have considerable drought resistance but yield poorly, have poor grain quality, and are susceptible to blast and lodging.

Research on drill-sown rice is conducted at the Agricultural Research Station, Mugad, Dharwar district. The work has recently been intensified in collaboration with IRRI and the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) center, Hyderabad. In the 1977 kharif season, the 1976 set of the International Upland Rice Yield Nursery (IURYN) was grown and evaluated at Mugad.

The best rated entries were IR2071-625-1-252 (5.1 t/ha), B541b-Kn-19-3-4 (5.0 t/ha), and IR1529-430-3 (4.9 t/ha). These entries are being promoted to minikit trials in the Karnataka area. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION Deepwater

Elongation ability and submergence tolerance of some deepwater (floating) rice varieties in Bangladesh

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Rice varieties were evaluated in 1978 for elongation ability and submergence tolerance. The varieties, except Haloi, represent popular deepwater (floating) rices in Bangladesh.

Materials were grown in pots in a net house. After 45 days, they were subjected to flooding and submergence. For evaluation of elongation ability, the pots containing the plants were suspended by ropes from iron bars and submerged in water in the deep flooded areas of Habiganj Rice Research Station, BRRI. The pots were kept under water so that about 20 cm of the leaves remained above the surface. Plant height above the water surface was readjusted daily for 10 days. For testing submergence tolerance, the pots were submerged below 20 cm water for 5 days.

The results are in the table. Rayada 16-04 was the shortest (64.0 cm) before flooding but its elongation ability was the highest (141%). Haloi, not a deepwater rice, was 81 cm tall before flooding, but had the lowest elongation ability (26%) and daily elongation rate (2.5 cm). Elongation ability and daily elongation were not identical (see table). The elongation rate was highest in Habiganj Aman 3 and 7 (12.3 cm). Habiganj Aman 1 was tallest (113 cm) before flooding but its elongation ability was 81% and elongation rate was 9.2 cm/day. In general, varieties such as Rayada, which are short before flooding, showed a low elongation rate but a high elongation ability. All the varieties showed little or no tolerance for submergence even at the age of 45 days.

The nature and range of elongation are shown in the graph. During the first

Plant elongation ability and submergence tolerance of deepwater (floating) rice varieties of Bangladesh, BRRI, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1978.

Variety	Plant ht before flooding ^a (cm)	Plant elongation ability ^b	Elongation (cm/day)	Submergence tolerance ^c
Habiganj Aman 1	113	81	9	5
Habiganj Aman 2	98	119	12	5
Habiganj Aman 3	92	134	12	6
Habiganj Aman 4	98	104	10	6
Habiganj Aman 5	91	121	11	6
Habiganj Aman 6	92	129	12	7
Habiganj Aman 7	103	119	12	6
Habiganj Aman 8	90	122	11	8
Rayada 15-01	88	99	9	6
Rayada 16-02	86	96	8	7
Rayada 16-04	64	141	9	6
Rayada 16-10	67	135	9	8
Lal Aman 6 34	83	104	9	8
Lal Aman 594	100	97	10	6
Lal Aman 127	95	96	9	8
Lal Aman 648	86	105	9	8
Kala Aman 735/1	74	129	10	9
Matia Aman 738/1	94	89	8	8
Matia Aman 5 75	96	110	10	8
Gowai 576	96	107	10	8
Haloi	87	28	2	7

^a Ht measured at 45 days after sowing.

^b Measured in percentage of height increase over basal height after 10 days of flooding.

^c Rated according to Standard Evaluation System for rice of IRTP 5 days after submergence.

Mean and range of elongation (cm/day) of floating rice varieties during 10 days of flooding, Joydebpur, Dacca.

3 days, elongation was fairly stable (10–11 cm/day), but on the 4th day, it suddenly rose to as high as 20 cm/day,

then dropped on the 5th to 7th days. On the 8th and 9th days, elongation rate rose slightly before it again stabilized.

The mechanism of deepwater effect on rice

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Some plants of the variety Krasnodarsky 424 were submerged in water for 72 hours at the 2-leaf stage while the control plants were not submerged. Every 24 hours the contents of ribonucleic acid (RNA) and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), the RNA:DNA ratio, the content of histones, and the ribonuclease (RNase) activity were determined in the plant apices.

The RNA:DNA ratio of submerged plants decreased (Fig. 1). Simultaneously

1. The dynamics of DNA:RNA ratio in apices of unsubmerged and submerged plants. Krasnodar, Kalinina, USSR.

2. The dynamics of ribonuclease (RNase) activity in apices of unsubmerged and submerged plants. Krasnodar, Kalinina, USSR.